

COGNITIVE APPROACH TO ANALYZE ALLUSIONS IN THE EXAMPLE OF 'ODE TO A NIGHTINGALE' BY KEATS JOHN

Askarova Maftuna Tulkin kizi

mrsmodest51@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13892427>

Abstract: The article attempts to illustrate the role of allusion in a literary work along with its cognitive peculiarities which will be analyzed within the framework of poetic text. The main purpose of the article is to show the function of the intertextual marker in the process of decoding imaginary descriptions and details hidden by the writer intended to be revealed.

Key words: allusion, intertextuality, precedent text, recipient text, myth, cognition, cognitive processing

INTRODUCTION

Since ancient time writers have been using stylistic devices in several purposes which have been always necessary to create successful intended impression on readers. Among these devices, intertextuality is still studied with a great interest and several peculiarities are being discovered on the basis of different literary works. The article mainly focuses on cognitive approach to the stylistic device.

Cognitive stylistics is a relatively new and also developing with fast pace of language studying which focuses on the interface between linguistics, literary studies and cognitive science. P. Simpson claims that cognitive stylistics mainly emphasize on mental representation rather than textual representation.

Prior to analyzing what has been intended to do in the article, the term intertextuality and one of its markers – allusion need to be defined to some extent. Shaping a particular text's meaning with the help of referencing another text is called intertextuality, which was first used and introduced to the science by Julia Kristeva, either through deliberate strategies such as allusion, quotation, parody and etc. or by interconnections between similar or related works perceived by a reader of the text. Intertextuality always contains 2 types of units one of which is a 'precedent text' that the borrowed fragment refers to and a 'recipient text' that uses the referred fragment in itself. Allusion is one of intertextual markers and a way of referring to another discourse. The main purpose of the article is to analyze allusion in the literary work with cognitive approach to it. Cognitive approach to stylistic devices is going beyond stylistic accounting for literary interpretation through linguistic models so as to investigate the commonalities and the idiosyncrasies in reading experiences

based on the relationship among the mind, language and the world. This will evoke the knowledge structure of humans and it is considered as a sign of cognition that will illustrate beyond the linguistic and stylistic features. John Keats' poem so-called 'Ode to a nightingale' was chosen so that allusion can be analyzed and its cognitive verbalization will be identified.

DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS

In the process of analyzing the creation and background of the poem and the poet plays really essential role. According to Stephen Hebron, the poem was inspired by a real-life situation and a bird, nightingale, which had built its nest close to the place where the author lived. The time when the ode was written is described as exceptionally fine summer weather and when the writer fell in love with his neighbor. The weather, season, feelings in writer's soul combined with soothing song of a nightingale inspired him to create his the most popular ode 'Ode to a nightingale', which symbolizes imagination between the mortals and the immortals. The title itself contains peculiarities need to be explained. The word 'ode' alludes to ancient Greek song which was performed mostly to praise, and the nightingale is addressed as a person and death and its harsh touches can be seen in the further lines, which demonstrates some life experiences of the poet who saw death of close people in an early age of childhood. The bird nightingale has almost acquired formulaic meaning of *the bird of spring, of night and of mourning* having been used since previous periods of literature. The writer considers it as the bridge between life and death, so devotes an ode to it. He perceives it as the border which could be crossed to the side of mortality or to the side of life. The bird's pleasant song inspires him to continue and believe bright future in life which can be ensured with the love in his heart. In the poem the writer depicts this all-in depth, yet eventually accepts the limitations of mortality.

In the first stanza the writer uses the allusion 'Lethe' ('One minute past, and Lethe – wards had sunk') which refers to Ancient Greek mythology. Lethe was a name of spirit of forgetfulness and also a name for one of five rivers of underworld of *Hades* (mythological character). This river was perceived that soul who drank from this river would forget previous life before reincarnation. This reference clearly depicts the intention of the poet to forget miserable days of the past and literally, drink from Lethe. In the next lines the writer gives the description of nature, particularly, forest and refers to a forest spirit called Dryad in Greek mythologies.

That thou, light-winged Dryad of the trees

*In some melodious plot
Of beechen green, and shadows numberless,
Singest of summer in full-throated ease.*

This allusion gives the whole scenery of woods with the reference of mythological spirit which signifies originally the value of trees.

In the second stanza the description of the environment is emphasized with the allusion of Flora which is originally a god of Plants, flowers and fertility in roman mythology. Any reader who has a background knowledge about these myths can easily grasp the function and the intention of its usage, and illustrates the scenery of the nature in green. The reference to Hippocrene, which was a fountain on Mount Helicon, where the Muses lived and is believed to inspire poetry in Greek mythology, shows overrising inspiration of the poet. These two allusions combine and depicts how the poet enjoyed and got inspired from the nature and its rebirth, and this is explained with the reference to Hippocrene to the readers.

In the fourth stanza the poet alludes to a Greek god of wine – Bacchus, and says not to follow him which means rejecting wine to travel and fly. The writer chooses in the next line a bird to travel and fly which means the inspiration of his poem.

*Away! away! for I will fly to thee,
Not charioted by Bacchus and his pards,
But on the viewless wings of Poesy,*

In the last stanza the poet emphasizes immortality referring to the bird and the allusion used in this case proved it to some extent. While mentioning emperors and kings who heard nightingale, the poet tries to make it even more clear and exaggerated with intertextuality. As mentioned above, the character of a nightingale has been used for a long time in literature and the writer uses allusion of Ruth who is a biblical character and is said to hear a nightingale while working in the field. With this example which dates back to Old Testimony time, the poet seems to have proven that a nightingale is immortality for him.

*In ancient days by emperor and clown:
Perhaps the self-same song that found a path
Through the sad heart of Ruth, when, sick for home,
She stood in tears amid the alien corn;
The same that oft-times hath
Charm'd magic casements, opening on the foam
Of perilous seas, in faery lands forlorn*

CONCLUSION

Concerning all abovementioned discussions and analysis, it can be concluded that the poem is constructed skillfully with allusions to other sources making the recipient text brief and intended by the poet. Allusions revealed what had been implied beyond the words which native speakers can use background knowledge and decode, and the imaginary world of the poet was also clarified with the usage of references he used in proper cases where they were relevant and necessary to broaden the meaning and explaining feelings of his. The allusion we analyzed clearly served their function to reveal what has been represented morally, beyond the text. The author skillfully managed to choose sensible references that can give a clear hint for his intention from other commonly familiar sources for target audience. On the other hand, for those who are not familiar with the culture, literature and history, may face some difficulties in decoding the meaning beyond allusive expressions which may not even seem as allusion and can be ignored.

References:

1. Abdul Bari Khan, Iram Zehra and Ghulam Hafsa, 'Stylistic analysis of the poem 'Ode to a nightingale' by John Keats', 2014
2. D. Ashurova, M. Galiyeva 'Stylistics', 2013
3. D. Ashurova, M. Galiyeva 'Cognitive linguistics, 2015
4. <https://spengtutor.blogspot.com/2017/08/in-to-nightingale-who-is-ruth-and-why.html>
5. allusion | Etymology, origin and meaning of allusion by etymonline
6. John Keats | Biography, Poems, Odes, Philosophy, Death, & Facts | Britannica

